

earlier¹⁰. The lines were determined by fitting the data to the equation :

$$-\frac{d\sigma}{dt} = K'\sigma = \frac{\sigma}{K}$$

(where σ = specific surface, K' = instability coefficient and K = stability coefficient) by the method of least squares. From the equation K' is measured. The reciprocal of this is a direct measure of stability coefficient (K) and is given in Table 1. It can be seen from the data of Table 1, that Dhavda, Salai, and Semla gums have the stability coefficient values at pH 10.1, 11.1, 9.2 (original pH of the gum suspension) respectively in the following order :

Semla > Dhavda < Salai

In the case of Kadai at pH 13.2, the emulsion was not possible, while in the case of Arabic gum at pH 11.9 the emulsion was possible but it was broken after three days ageing time.

At pH 9, 6, 3 the stability coefficient values of various gums can be arranged in following orders :

Salai > Semla > Dhavda > Arabic > Kadai (at pH 9)

Salai > Dhavda > Arabic > Semla > Kadai (at pH 6)

Dhavda > Kadai > Arabic > Salai > Semla (at pH 3)

Hydrogen ion concentration plays an important role in all the cases, as is evident from the particle size distribution, experimentally as well as graphically determined initial specific areas and the stability coefficient values as is evident from the data of Table 1.

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Entropy Variations of Normal-alkyl Derivatives of Organic Compounds

R. S. ROY

Institut für Strahlenchemie im Max-Planck-Institut für Kohlenforschung, Stiftstrasse 34-36, D-4330 Mülheim a.d. Ruhr, W.-Germany

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THE homologous series of organic compounds provide a convenient basis for studying the physico-chemical properties of organic compounds. Relationships between the bulk properties of these have recently been established^{1,2,3}. It has been shown that the bulk properties can be expressed as an additive function of the number of carbon atoms, n_c , present in the molecule. Prediction of values of entropy for the normal alkyl derivatives of compounds of homologous series with different functional groups is possible as outlined in this work.

Entropy data as reported by Rossini *et al* on these compounds at 298°K in the gaseous state, are plotted against the number of carbon atoms in the molecule in Fig. 1. It is seen that the entropy of these molecules is a linear function of the number of carbon atoms in the molecule. Minor deviations from linearity are observed with the first two members of a series, in that the entropy is slightly less than expected. For example, in the alkane series the observed entropy for CH₄ is 44.52 cal/mol-deg while the expected value is 45.7 cal/mol-deg from the S° vs n_c curve. This variation in the general trend for the first two members of a series has also been observed earlier^{1,2,3} in the studies of their physico-chemical properties.

The interesting feature of these curves is that the slope in all the cases remains the same being equal to 9.4. It is thus shown that S° is related to n_c of a compound in a series according to equation

$$S^\circ = Nn_c + C \quad \dots (1)$$

where c is a constant characteristic of a compound with a functional group, and N a universal constant of 9.4. Values of C have been estimated from Fig. 1 as 36.5, 40.5, 44.5, 48, 49.5, 50, 50.5, 52, 56.5 and 63.5 for alkanes, nitriles, aldehydes, (fluoro compounds and ethers), alcohols (chloro compounds), amines, sulphides, bromo compounds iodo compounds (thiols and esters), nitro compounds, and nitrates respectively. The substitution of different functional groups in a normal paraffin hydrocarbon produces a significant effect on C , and the compounds with different functional groups can be placed in a series in the order: alkane < nitrile < fluoro = aldehyde ether < alcohol = chloro < amine < sulphide < bromo < iodo = ester < thiol < nitro < nitrate.

It can thus be demonstrated that the entropy of a molecule is additive in nature, depending only on the nature of groups present, each CH₂ group contributing a value of 9.4 cal/mol-deg towards the entropy. Deduction of the entropy value for a

Fig. 1. ○—Alkane; ○—Ether, Fluoro, Aldehyde; △—Iodo, Thiol, Ester; ○—Amine; ×—Nitrile; φ—Nitrate; ⊖—Nitro; ⊗—Chloro, Alcohol; ⊕—Bromo; □—Sulphide.

compound within these series becomes possible, provided the value of C for the particular series is known.

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Chemical Examination of the Bark of *Terminalia myriocarpa*-Heurek and Muell-Arg

S. P. DHOUBHADEL and GRIHA MAN SINGH
Department of Chemistry, Tribhuvan University,
Kirtipur, Kathmandu, Nepal

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VARIOUS species of the genus *Terminalia* (family: Combretaceae) have been investigated by different workers¹⁻⁵ and have been shown to contain tomentolic, gallic, chebulic, chebulinic, arjunolic

acids, β -sitosterol, sapogenins and hydroxy stilbene glucoside etc. Literature survey indicated that no work has so far been reported on the chemical constituents of *Terminalia myriocarpa*. *Terminalia myriocarpa* is a very large evergreen woody tree, the bark of which is used as a potent cardiac stimulant and mild diuretic⁶⁻⁷. This paper reports the general phytochemical screening and the systematic examination of the bark of the plant.

The alcoholic extract of the bark was tested with Mayer and Dragendroff reagents, Libermann-Burchard reagent, Kedde reagent, Shinoda reagent and for froth formation. In all the tests, the responses were negative indicating the absence of alkaloids, steroids, triterpenoids, cardenolides, flavonoids and saponoids from the bark.

Experimental

The powdered bark (142 g) was refluxed with petrol (1/1) for 18 hrs. The extract on concentration gave a syrupy liquid which on column chromatography over neutral alumina using petroleum ether-benzene (1 : 1), yielded β -sitosterol confirmed by comparison with authentic sample (m.p., mixed m.p. and co-tlc).

The defatted bark was then extracted with chloroform (800 ml) for 10 hrs. The concentrated extract (0.90 g) on trituration with petroleum ether gave an insoluble portion (0.06 g) which did not respond to triterpenoid and saponin tests and was found to be the same substance as that obtained in the methanolic extract by co-tlc, uv and ir comparisons.

The above bark residue was then extracted with methanol (1/1) for 12 hrs. The dark red solid residue left after concentrating the extract, was triturated with water to yield water insoluble colourless solid (2.1 g). The aqueous portion responded to Molish, Fehling and Seliwanoff tests positively and the sugar was identified as fructose by comparison with authentic sample (co-PC, *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water, v/v 4 : 1 : 5, Rf 0.19; *n*-butanol-benzene pyridine-water, v/v 5 : 1 : 3 : 3, Rf. 0.28, spray reagent aniline hydrogen phthalate).

The water insoluble residue was found to be a single substance by tlc (silica gel, water-acetic acid-conc. hydrochloric acid, v/v 1 : 3 : 3, Rf 0.81, NH₃/black spot) and was recrystallised from pyridine into yellow needles, m.p. above 360°. Found : C, 55.71%; H, 2.12%; Calcd. for C₁₄H₈O₈; C, 55.62%; H, 1.98%. It gave a green ferric reaction and negative response to Molish and Fehling tests. It was insoluble in sodium bicarbonate but soluble in sodium carbonate and sodium hydroxide solutions and was reprecipitated by hydrochloric acid, $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH})$ 258 & 357 nm $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH}-\text{NaOAc})$, 259 & 347 nm, $\nu_{\max}(\text{Nujol})$ 3350, 1700, 1610 cm⁻¹. It gave a tetracetate (NaOAc/Ac₂O) crystallizing from acetic anhydride as pale creamy crystals, m.p. 348-350°; lit⁸, m.p. 350-352°; Found : C, 56.24%; H, 3.22%; Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₄O₁₂; C, 56.00%; H, 3.0% $\lambda_{\max}(\text{EtOH})$